

INNOVATION MANAGEMENT, GOVERNMENT POLICY, INNOVATIVE LEADERSHIP, AND AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY INFLUENCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF USED CAR SALES BUSINESS OPERATORS IN BANGKOK METROPOLITAN REGION

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Abstract

The used car sales business is a business that was created to meet the needs of consumers who want to use used cars in their daily lives, both for business and personal use. Selling used cars is a type of business that is highly competitive and constantly facing changes, having to compete with the new car market that has incentives in terms of both price and latest technology and facing the strategies of new car manufacturers wanting to increase their market share, government tax policies supporting the use of electric cars, and new forms of market competition that change with the growth of the online market. This research aims to 1) study the level of innovation management, government policy, innovative leadership, automotive technology, and competitiveness of used car sales business operators in Bangkok and surrounding areas. 2) Study the influence of innovation management, government policy, innovative leadership, and automotive technology on the competitiveness of used car sales business operators in Bangkok and surrounding areas. 3) Develop a competitiveness model for used car entrepreneurs in the Bangkok Metropolitan Region. This research uses a combined research method between quantitative research and qualitative research. The quantitative research, the sample consisted of 320 used car business operators in Bangkok and surrounding areas. The sample size was determined using the criterion of 20 times the observed variable. A multi-stage random sampling method was used. Use questionnaires to collect data. Data were analyzed using structural equation modeling. The qualitative research used in-depth interviews. The main informants were used car entrepreneurs and used car sales experts, totaling 20 people. The research results found that 1) innovation management, government policy, innovative leadership, automotive technology, and the competitiveness of used car sales business operators in Bangkok Metropolitan Region are high. 2) Manage innovation, government policy, innovative leadership, and automotive technology that affect the competitiveness of used car sales business operators in Bangkok Metropolitan Region with statistical significance at 0.05. 3) The competitiveness model of used car sales entrepreneurs in Bangkok Metropolitan Region that the researcher developed is called the LTMP-CUCB Model (L = Innovative Leadership, T = Automotive Technology, M= Innovation Management, P = Government Policy, CUCB = Competitiveness of Used Cars Business in The Bangkok Metropolitan Region.) In addition, the results of qualitative research found that to create success for used car entrepreneurs, they must have complete services and networks of business partners, add convenient and fast contact channels for customers, and add online used car trading platforms to respond to customer needs directly and quickly with maximum efficiency. The results of this research can be used as a guideline for setting policies for business operations and promoting the success of the used car sales business in the Bangkok Metropolitan Region in the future.

Keyword: Innovative Leadership /Automotive Technology /Competitiveness / Selling Used Cars Entrepreneurs.

INTRODUCTION

The ability to compete in business refers to an organization's capacity to produce goods or services that meet customer needs better than competitors, both in terms of price and quality, while still generating good profits. This involves anticipating and offering innovative products and services that align with market demands, achieving a goal of exceeding customer needs beyond competitors and ensuring the organization's sustainability. Competitiveness is not just about offering competitively priced products and services; it also impacts the efficiency of the organization (Tomalá & Olives, 2022).

Additionally, competitiveness also entails operating efficiently, reducing costs without compromising quality, including optimizing procurement processes by sourcing materials at the best possible prices while maintaining high standards in product and service quality. Competitiveness is about creating value for customers through innovation, efficiency, and differentiation from competitors. By continuously improving business models and products/services, organizations can maintain a competitive edge over others and achieve long-term success (Torki et al., 2021; Volberda, Van Den Bosch & Heij, 2013).

Given these considerations, researchers have studied the competitiveness of the car dealership business. They have examined variables such as innovation management, government policies, innovative leadership, and automotive technology that affect the competitiveness of car dealership businesses. This study has been informed by relevant research documents and literature. Thus, it contributes to the understanding of innovation management, government policies, innovative leadership, and automotive technology's impact on the competitiveness of car dealership businesses in the Bangkok metropolitan area and its surrounding regions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Government policy plays a crucial role in creating an environment conducive to competition in business by providing opportunities and space for thriving and competitive businesses and trading partners in the economy effectively and sustainably. Appropriate policies involve opening up opportunities for businesses across all sectors of society and the economy. Government policies can create an environment that supports businesses in the country by reducing legal barriers and regulations or necessary measures to ensure fair and open competition. A favorable environment can help businesses better compete and innovate (Kerdpitak et al., 2023). Additionally, government policies are significant factors in supporting and stimulating innovation development (Liu, 2018), which in turn enhances businesses' competitiveness in rapidly growing sectors and links to the country's success in innovation-driven economic eras. Policies promoting both direct and indirect investments are highly reliant on infrastructure. Understanding how these policies affect customers' perceptions and behaviors helps various businesses support the positive impact of policy-making on governments, industries, and customers in the future (Aman-Ullah et al., 2022; Mohi et al., 2018).

Innovative leadership plays a significant role in guiding and managing organizations. Leaders with these characteristics often have the ability to generate creative ideas and innovations to solve problems and improve processes or products. This supports and promotes innovation. Innovative leaders can create an environment that fosters innovation and stimulates challenges within the organization to enhance learning and adaptability to change.

Innovation is a beneficial and efficient operation for organizations, as it creates innovative business methods. Nowadays, creativity is seen as a powerful tool for success and a key factor in innovative leadership practices. Innovative leaders must be aware of and understand the problems of their personnel and establish new approaches and methods to solve them.

They need to understand the rules, processes, principles, and technologies within the organization to identify what and why problem-solving is necessary (Şen, Kabak & Yangınlar, 2013). Innovative leaders often focus on building understanding and collaboration within their teams to successfully create innovation and change. They can lead organizations at the forefront of market and industry changes.

Additionally, innovative leaders can foster understanding and collaboration within teams and organizations to collectively create sustainable innovation and change in the long term. Therefore, innovative leadership influences and plays a crucial role in managing and creating efficient and growing organizations in rapidly changing current and future situations (Şen & Eren, 2012; Rübmann et al., 2015; Riza, 2020).

Automotive technology pertains to the development associated with the creation of engines, fuel systems, ignition systems, brakes, power transmission systems, electronic equipment, diagnostics, and others for vehicles or self-propelled machinery used in standard cars, sports cars, trailers, marine vehicles, and others (Stoltz, 2021). Automotive technology focuses on inspection, maintenance, and repair of vehicles.

Related occupations include automotive mechanics, diesel service technicians, auto body shops, service writers, warranty specialists, industrial production managers, mechanical engineers, and others (Bakersfield, 2023; Ariffin & Sahid, 2017). Automotive technology is thus pivotal in the automotive industry, significantly impacting the economy and society.

The automotive industry is crucial in the economies of many countries, generating jobs and income for entrepreneurs and laborers and driving the nation's economy (Bakersfield, 2023). Automotive technology greatly affects sales in the automotive sector and related businesses. Innovations in automotive technology enable companies to develop new products with new features and functions, attracting new customers and retaining existing ones (Gardner, 2007; Breznik & Hisrich, 2014; Park et al., 2011).

Management innovation is of paramount importance in an era characterized by rapid change and fierce competition. Innovation is a key factor in responding to market changes and customer demands, enabling organizations to adapt flexibly and compete effectively in a rapidly changing environment. While technological innovation is undoubtedly crucial, studies have identified management innovation as an innovation that can lead to successful operations

beyond the scope of technology. It is a more complex form of innovation in terms of replication and may support long-term competitive advantage (Goyal & Pitt, 2007; Ghodang, 2021). Governments have begun to adopt management innovation in operations, aligning with organizations for cooperation and economic development (OECD, 2009).

Innovation plays a significant role as a driver of economic, social, and environmental change. Factors related to innovation have received increasing attention and continuous roles. Innovation is a broad concept covering various activities and processes, including market dynamics, entrepreneurship, networks, and competition, as well as skills and organizational aspects, creativity, and knowledge transfer (Hamel, 2006; Heij et al., 2020; Mol & Birkinshaw, 2012).

Competitiveness is a crucial advantage for organizations amidst competition in conducting business. Creating better value for customers is one way to enhance competitive advantage. This can be achieved through various means such as pricing strategies, superior quality, and rapid responsiveness to changing customer needs compared to competitors (Dereli, 2015; Distanont & Khongmalai, 2018).

Competitive advantage entails building capabilities superior to competitors. A country's competitive capability depends on the ability of its industries to innovate and elevate the level of competitiveness within the industry. Benefits from competition drive entrepreneurs to adapt to various pressures and seek benefits from such competition (Porter, 1990). Competitiveness also helps organizations remain stable and cope with changing customer demands efficiently, fostering sustainability and success in an era of intense competition and rapid change (Dereli, 2015).

Competition and innovation, driven by the forces of the new economy, are related to the efficiency of investment returns when organizations accumulate innovations (Alberti, 2014). Technological competition tends to create incentives and drive innovation, with conditions of appropriate profit distribution serving as a starting point for technology development and subsequent innovation (Liu & Jiang, 2016; Pangpriree & Penpokai, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The mixed methods research, with Embedded Design, was conducted by integrating quantitative and qualitative research methods. The study primarily began with quantitative research, involving a literature review and analysis of documents and research works related to variables that affect the competitiveness of business entrepreneurs selling used cars.

These variables included Innovation management, government policy, innovative leadership and automotive technology. Data was synthesized and summarized into specific research definitions. The population was 403 business entrepreneurs selling used cars in Bangkok and surrounding areas. The quantitative research sample size was determined by estimating the size of 20 times greater than the number of observed variables (Hair et al., 2011). In this research, there were 16 observed variables, so the researchers determined a sample size of 320 by using a simple random.

Measurement indicators for variables were defined within the research conceptual framework. Subsequently, these indicators were used to develop a questionnaire based on a 5-Point Likert scale (Likert, 1932). Prior to data collection, the validity and reliability of the measurement tools were tested.

The collected data were then subjected to statistical analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique. For qualitative research, the researchers employed in-depth interview methods with 10 business entrepreneurs selling used cars and 10 experts in selling used car business, totaling 20 key informants. Purposive sampling was used. The qualitative data was then organized, categorized, analyzed, interpreted, connected, concluded to enable detailed and reasoned explanations in the quantitative analysis.

RESULTS

The normal distribution of the 18 observed variables studied in the structural equation model was examined, using the chi-square test (χ^2). The statistical significance at the .05 level represented non-normally distribution of such variables. On the other hand, if it was found to be not statistically significant (P-value > .50), it revealed normal distribution of such variables, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of observed variables)n=320(

Variable	\bar{X}	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
ECON	4.18	.83	19.97	-2.829	-1.366	9.871	.007
SECI	3.70	.86	23.38	-1.356	-.299	1.929	.381
ENVI	3.84	.89	23.26	-1.788	-.834	3.894	.143
CREA	3.85	.92	24.05	-1.880	-.803	4.180	.124
VISI	3.71	.85	22.90	-1.342	-.198	1.839	.399
TEAM	3.63	.77	21.33	-.629	-.111	.408	.816
FRUG	4.00	.79	19.84	-1.920	-.969	4.625	.099
SAFE	3.90	.71	18.31	-1.387	.736	2.464	.292
DURA	4.14	.72	17.47	-1.676	-1.018	3.847	.146
PROD	3.76	.82	21.78	-1.199	-.599	1.797	.407
SERV	4.04	.76	18.78	-1.895	-1.946	7.379	.025
MARK	3.81	.86	22.71	-2.028	-1.773	7.259	.027
ORAG	3.94	.84	21.40	-1.912	-1.726	6.633	.036
COST	3.92	.71	18.17	-1.188	-.054	1.413	.493
QUAL	3.90	.71	18.37	-1.031	-.184	1.098	.578
RESP	4.19	.80	19.18	-3.264	-2.032	14.778	.001

Note: chi-square (χ^2) with statistical significance (P-value <.05) indicates a non-normal distribution

The researchers have checked the quality of the variables studied in the model by testing construct validity of each latent variable using the Confirm Factor Analysis technique by considering the greater than .30 standardized factor loadings to confirm a good observed variable.

It was considered from the R^2 to check reliability of the empirical variables as well as directly examining the Construct Reliability ($\rho_c > .60$) of the latent variables and Average Variable Extracted ($\rho_v > 0.50$), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Factor Loadings (n = 320)

Variables	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	t	R ²
Government Policy)GOPOL)				
Economy (ECON)	.62	.21	9.77	.79
Society)SECI)	.66	.27	10.23	.73
Environment)ENVI)	.71	.50	10.76	.50
Innovative Leadership)INOLED)				
Creativity (CREA)	.62	.41	10.33	.59
Vision)VISI)	.73	.46	11.88	.54
Teamwork (TEAM)	.73	.47	11.82	.53
Automotive Technology)ATMT)				
Frugality (FRUG)	.47	.38	7.34	.62
Safety (SAFE)	.73	.37	9.93	.63
Duration (DURA)	.71	.39	9.80	.61
Innovation Management)INOMG)				
Product Innovation (PROD)	.43	.31	6.12	.69
Service Innovation)SERV)	.67	.34	7.71	.66
Market Innovation (MARK)	.54	.31	6.58	.69
Organizational Innovation)ORAG)	.47	.18	5.77	.82
Competitiveness)COMPT)				
Cost (COST)	.85	.28	14.54	.72
Quality (QUAL)	.69	.53	11.92	.47
Responsiveness (RESP)	.65	.58	11.27	.42
$\rho_c = .78, \rho_v = .54$				
Chi-Square=0.00, df=0, P-value=1.00000, RMSEA=0.000				

Table 3: Direct effect, indirect effect, and total effect)n=320(

Dependent Variables	R ²	Effects	Independent Variables			
			Innovation Management)INOMG)	Government Policy)GOPOL)	Innovative Leadership)INOLED)	Automotive Technology)ATMT)
Innovation Management)INOMG)	.80	DE	-	.42*(10.92)	.65*(10.84)	.62*(9.09)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.42*(10.92)	.65*(10.84)	.62*(9.09)
Competitiveness)COMPT)	.85	DE	.62*(8.76)	.51*(10.40)	.72*(10.43)	.64*(10.48)
		IE	-	.38*(6.77)	.21*(6.94)	.24*(6.86)
		TE	.62*(8.76)	.89*(9.19)	.93*(9.24)	.88*(9.56)
$\chi^2 = 157.12$ df = 91 p-value = .00002, $\chi^2 / df = 1.72$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .028, SRMR = .044, CFI = .98, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 260.86						

*statistical significance at the .05 level

Note: In parentheses, they were the t-value. If the value was not between -1.96 and 1.96, it was statistically significant at the .05 level. DE=Direct Effect, IE=Indirect Effect, TE=Total Effect

Table 1: The adjusted model (n=320)

Chi-Square=157.12, df=91, P-value=0.00002, RMSEA=0.048

The results of the data analysis indicated that the model was fit with the observational data by allowing the variance of standard errors (θ) of the 3 pairs of observed variables to have a relationship, with degrees of freedom (df) before adjustment being 160 and df after adjustment being 138, it was found that the adjusted model fitted well with the observational data. This conclusion was based on fit indices as follows: $\chi^2 = 157.12$, $df = 91$, $p\text{-value} = .00002$, $\chi^2/df = 1.72$, $RMSEA = .048$, $RMR = .028$, $SRMR = .044$, $CFI = .98$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 260.86$, as shown in Table 3 and Figure 1.

The results of the goodness-of-fit index revealed that $\chi^2 = 157.12$, $df = 91$, $p\text{-value} = .00002$, not meeting the statistical significance criterion ($P\text{-value} > .05$). However, the χ^2 was sensitive to sample size. The χ^2/df of $1.72 < 2.00$ within an acceptable range was considered. Other acceptable fit indices are as follows: $RMSEA = .048 < .05$, $RMR = .028 < .05$, $SRMR = .044 < .05$, $CFI = .98 > .97$, $GFI = .94 > .90$, $AGFI = .91 > .90$, and $CN = 260.86 > 200.00$. Based on these goodness-of-fit indices, it concluded that the adjusted structural equation model fitted well with the observational data. The parameter estimates in the model were considered acceptable.

CONCLUSION

The study found that the adjusted structural equation model of Innovation management, government policy, innovative leadership and automotive technology that affected the

competitiveness of business entrepreneurs selling used cars in Bangkok and surrounding areas was fit to the existing data in the acceptable level. The fit indices were as follows: $\chi^2 = 157.12$, $df = 91$, $p\text{-value} = .00002$, $\chi^2/df = 1.72$, $RMSEA = .048$, $RMR = .028$, $SRMR = .044$, $CFI = .98$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 260.86$. The model's estimates are presented as follows:

- 1) Innovation management (INOMG) has a direct influence on Competitiveness (COMPT) with an effect coefficient of $.62^*(8.76)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 1, innovation management has a direct and positive influence on the competitiveness of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 2) Government policy (GOPOL) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INOMG) with an effect coefficient of $.42^*(10.92)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 2, government policy has a direct and positive influence on innovation management of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 3) Government policy (GOPOL) has a direct influence on Competitiveness (COMPT) with an effect coefficient of $.51^*(10.40)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 3, government policy has a direct and positive influence on the competitiveness of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 4) Innovative leadership (INOLED) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INOMG) with an effect coefficient of $.65^*(10.84)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 4, innovative leadership has a direct and positive influence on innovation management of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 5) Innovative leadership (INOLED) has a direct influence on Competitiveness (COMPT) with an effect coefficient of $.72^*(10.43)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 5, innovative leadership has a direct and positive influence on the competitiveness of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 6) Automotive technology (ATMT) has a direct influence on Innovation Management (INOMG) with an effect coefficient of $.62^*(9.09)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 6, automotive technology has a direct and positive influence on innovation management of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 7) Automotive technology (ATMT) has a direct influence on Competitiveness (COMPT) with an effect coefficient of $.64^*(10.48)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 7, automotive technology has a direct and positive influence on the competitiveness of business entrepreneurs selling used cars, is supported.
- 8) Government Policy (GOPOL), Innovative Leadership (INOLED) and Automotive Technology (ATMT) can jointly predict Innovation Management (INOMG) by 80 percent.
- 9) Innovation Management (INOMG), Government Policy (GOPOL), Innovative Leadership (INOLED) and Automotive Technology (ATMT) can jointly predict Competitiveness (COMPT) by 85 percent.

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